

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC METHODS OF DEVELOPING LINGUISTIC
COMPETENCES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION MOTHER TONGUE AND
READING LITERACY CLASSES.

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Abstract: In this article, the psycholinguistic methods of developing linguistic competences in mother tongue and reading literacy classes of primary education are scientifically and theoretically analyzed.

Key words: Speech activity, ontogenesis, science, Uzbek, development, current stage, tasks, methods and materials, interconnected, a number of studies, forms, etc.

Introduction: The interest of humanities scientists in the problem of ontogenetic development of communicative competence in our country is increasing every year. Various terms have been proposed to describe the science of child speech, including: psychology of child speech and child linguistics, discourse, ontolinguistics, developmental linguistics, and theory of logogenesis. etc. However, the science of the ontogenesis of speech activity, even at the current stage of its development, appears in the form of a series of studies that are poorly connected with each other in terms of tasks, methods and materials. This is mainly due to the fact that children's speech is studied by scientists from different scientific fields, and sometimes from different disciplines.

Literature review: Children's traditional speech is the object of research by linguists, psychologists, speech therapists. Teachers specializing in mother tongue teaching at school. At the same time, a strong impetus for the development of the science of children's speech was the "anthropocentric explosion" that language science experienced in our country in the last twenty years. Anthropocentric linguistics (neolinguistics) does not focus on the description of the language structure, but on the study of the person of the language, that is, the person in his communicative competence. Today, neolinguistics combines various directions of non-traditional cognitive-communicative linguistics: psycho-, pragma, sociolinguistics, text linguistics, discursive linguistics, etc. etc. In the works of non-linguists, the ontogeny of speech is very often a topic or educational material. Over the past two decades, the science that we traditionally call linguistics has changed significantly. The fact is that at this time important discoveries were made that increased the volume of linguistic knowledge. The contours of the boundaries of linguistics

have changed, the ideas about its subject matter, its internal fragmentation existing old parts, the reconstruction of the whole old and good building. The main reason that started the process of changing the general space of language science was the bold and enthusiastic invasion of some linguists into related fields of knowledge. From -The science of caste, whose efforts are aimed at the immanent description of intralinguistic relations, linguistics is now regaining the status of a humanistic (from human) field of knowledge and becoming a science that is more and more oriented to life. The result of this was the emergence of "new" linguistics in our country (speech linguistics, psycho-, social-, pragmatic, text linguistics, etc.), the revival of classical rhetoric, the formation of neo-rhetoric based on it, its practical field. humanitarian knowledge designed to influence the development of communication skills of a person. Currently, ontolinguistics occupies a huge scientific space in science, it studies the ontogenesis of speech, the process of developing communication tools in a child. Knowledge of laws The development of human speech is not only theoretical, but, I would say, of national importance. Every parent, teacher, school teacher, psychologist, speech therapist, coach, university lecturer, doctor, etc. It is necessary (I emphasize this word) to know how to develop the ability to communicate with a child, teenager, young man. How does this process relate to the development of the intelligence of the developing individual? What is the role of people surrounding the child? They need to know what contributes to and encourages its normal, full course, and what can interfere with the evolution of speech, disrupt it. This knowledge can save a little person from big problems in his future life. They can help all of us to raise a healthy, well-rounded generation, the generation of future citizens of our country. In addition, ontopsy-Holinguistics performs a task familiar to the humanities: it allows to build a bridge between people of different ages and help society solve the eternal problem of fathers and children. In our country, there are scientific centers that are tasked with the scientific and civilian study of the little-known laws of the development of the speech and thinking of a person who is developing literally before our eyes, and the search for mechanisms of influence on it. started his linguistic identity. In Russia, they appeared everywhere: in Moscow, Saratov, Samara, Voronezh, Orel, Taganrog, Kemerovo, Tomsk, Vladivostok and other cities. The largest school of ontolinguistics appeared in St. Petersburg (Leningrad at that time), and as a "scientific Mecca" the head of the newly established "Children's speech" department, Professor S.N. Zeitlin. Thanks to the efforts of S. N. Tseitlin at the Russian State Pedagogical University. A.I. Hertsen (I

repeat) created a unique department of children's speech, in which a workshop on ontological speech problems has been working for twenty years. genesis of linguistic consciousness. Within the framework of the seminar, preliminary defenses of candidacy and doctoral dissertations, meetings, conferences and symposia are held, and many collections of scientific articles, monographs, and training manuals are published.

Conclusion: The atmosphere of tolerance and interest in different points of view, in which the author of these lines is a constant participant, which always prevails in these scientific meetings, allowed the department to strengthen the achievements of scientists of various fields of linguistics and other disciplines. The St. Petersburg School of Children's Speech Linguistics experienced the beneficial influence of anthropocentrism and primarily psycholinguistics in its development.

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